

1 Towards a Mobile-based ADAS Simulation Framework

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1.1 Abstract

The increasing number of vehicles and mobile users has led to a huge increase in the development of Advanced Driver Assistance Systems (ADAS). In this paper we propose a multi-agent-based driving simulator which integrates a test-bed that allows ADAS developers to compress testing time and carry out tests in a controlled environment while using a low-cost setup. We use the SUMO microscopic simulator and a serious-game-based driving simulator which has geodata provided from standard open sources. This simulator connects to an Android device and sends data such as the current GPS coordinates and transportation network data. One important feature of this application is that it allows ADAS validation without the need of field testing. Also important is the suitability of our architecture to serve as an appropriate means to conduct behaviour elicitation through peer-designed agents, as well as to collect performance measures related to drivers' interaction with ADAS solutions.

Keywords: Mobile ADAS, Driving Simulators, Serious Games, SUMO.

1.2 Introduction

The technological advances on both the mobile and transportation industries are remarkable. This has made the development of ADAS an interesting topic [1]. However, even though most high-end cars nowadays ship with built-in embedded systems, most of the older cars do not have such devices. This brings about an interesting research opportunity, which is to develop and test ADAS that run on low-cost devices, such as an Android tablet or smartphone.

The main goal of this paper is to describe the methodology of our MultiAgent System (MAS) based driving simulator, integrating SUMO microscopic simulator with driving simulators. We also intend to describe our implementation of a test-bed to easily develop ADAS using the system, simulating their use in a low-cost and controlled environment.

There are several benefits to testing an ADAS in a simulated environment rather than on a real scenario. As the tests are not conducted in a real physical location, they are not subjected to travel times, traffic or other adverse conditions which could render them mute. This, as well as being able to deploy the simulator in low-cost computers, and therefore reaching more test subjects, leads to time compression of the tests. Noticeably, cost reduction is another significant benefit as the electrical cost of running a simulator is dismissive when compared to fuel costs of real world testing. Besides preventing the safety risks inherent to

driving, simulation allows us to control the test environment and manipulate it according to the specificities of the ADAS being tested.

The objective of our work was to develop the MAS and include a test-bed that was easy to implement and replicate in low-cost environments. We aimed to combine SUMO microscopic simulator with IC-DEEP, which is a driving simulator developed at LIACC [2], with the GeoStream framework developed at SI&CG, as well as to enhance them with logs of simulated GPS positions in a mobile device. To achieve so, a mobile application/service was developed in order to receive this communication from the simulator and override the default GPS sensor of the device. We wanted to make it easy to extend the communication between the simulator and a mobile device, providing the latter with more information such as the current speed limit, semaphoric information, or other data from the network.

This work aims to contribute with a novel multi-faceted methodology to simulate and research multiple human factors in Intelligent Transportation Systems (ITS) and, particularly, with a novel approach to test ADAS that will enable developers to validate and test their applications more easily and efficiently while reducing costs.

In the following sections we describe the development and results of our implementation. In section 3 we introduce some related state-of-the-art works on the subject of ITS, focusing on simulation, on the integration of different scope simulators and also on the topic of serious games. We then describe our approach, architecture and development details. Finally we present our preliminary verification as well as their analysis in section 5. We finish this paper with a set of conclusions and interesting future work.

1.3 Background & Related Work

The Artificial Transportation Systems (ATS) [3], [4] concept has been one of the main research topics in the IEEE ITS Society [5]. A typical approach to ATS modeling and development is the MAS metaphor. Another potentially concomitant approach is the HLA concept. The concept is based on the idea of distributed simulation, so as to meet the requirements of all usages and users rather than of a single simulation model and analysis perspective [6].

In [7], authors propose to integrate a driving simulator and a traffic microsimulator, in an attempt to tackle the mutual-dependence between the driver's behavior and traffic conditions.

Combining SUMO microscopic traffic simulation [8], using MAS capabilities, with other simulators has also been researched [9]. Authors in [6] have studied a HLA-based approach to simulate electric vehicles in Simulink and SUMO. Driver-centric simulation has been researched by authors in [10], where they have developed a simulation tool that provides feedback back to the network based on the driver's behaviour.

Driving simulators are no doubt an important tool when researching ATS, specially so when studying the influence of human factors in driving faults [2]. These faults often occur in direct consequence of performing secondary tasks while driving [11]. In [12] authors introduce a game-engine-based for modeling and computing platform for ATS. They describe the artificial population both in their macroscopic and microscopic aspects.

Regarding driving simulators with ADAS testing capabilities, authors in [13] propose a reconfigurable driving simulator with several components to accommodate different ADAS testing or training. A framework for ADAS assessment and benchmarking has been developed by [14], with configurable scenarios and 3D scenes and multiple sensors input.

Authors in [15] developed a Full Speed Range Adaptive Cruise Control with their platform for ADAS prototyping and evaluation, SiVIC. The platform is capable of reproducing vehicle and sensor behaviors in a realistic fashion, according to the configured environment in the simulator. The developed platform also simulates noised and imperfect data.

A system comprising a large scale driving simulator, built in a 360 deg full dome with 3D scenes from real city area has been developed by [16]. The system contains a multitude of features such as real-time hardware-in-the-loop, wireless communication devices and bio signal analysis and is used to develop and test ADAS as well as Advanced Safety Vehicle, ITS infrastructure and others.

1.4 Methodological Approach

The proposed system architecture is as described in Figure 1-1. The main module of the system is the SUMO simulator, which is responsible for the network's multi-agent microscopic simulation, and has multiple driving agents. This module provides an overview of the whole MAS and can be manipulated directly.

The SUMO module also acts as a "central server", providing all the essential information for both IC-DEEP and the High Fidelity Simulator. This information consists of the network infrastructure and the agents in the system, whereas terrain morphology and road or building geometry are provided by the GeoStream framework.

Both of the driving simulators have a local representation of the whole MAS and are capable of controlling any driving agent. The simulators are also able to connect to an Android device and pass along all the information deemed necessary, such as the GPS coordinates of the current driving agent being controlled. The Android device is running a service that receives the incoming connections from the simulator and also the ADAS being tested. The dotted area in Figure 1-1 corresponds to the developed components as of the writing of this paper.

Figure 1-1: Overview of the system's architecture

1.4.1 Simulators & GeoStream Framework

The proposed system architecture has two simulators; however, as of the writing of this paper, only the IC-DEEP simulator has been enhanced and integrated into the framework. The latter is implemented in Unity3D and has the GeoStream framework embedded directly. The GeoStream framework connects with OpenStreetMaps, Google Geolocation API, Google Altitude API and other data providers in order to fetch the required geographical information

of a given location and remodel it in a fashion which can be interpreted by all the simulators in a coherent and consistent way. This is specially important to the SUMO microscopic simulator as the raw network data imported from OpenStreetMaps, typically, generates unrealistic ways and intersections. The information generated by GeoStream framework is then parsed into both simulators to generate a 3D scene that is representative of the chosen test location.

1.4.2 Mobile Device

The Android service sets the current GPS location using *MockLocation* API to override the default location provider. All applications running on the mobile device that use or perceive the current location will also be affected by the running service.

The new GPS coordinates are sent from the simulator every second; however, this value is a parameter of the simulator and so can be adjusted to the specific needs of each scenario. The developed service can be run as a standalone application, and thus testing the ADAS mobile applications independently, as shown in the left side of Figure 1-2. There is also the option to use the service as a library in any Android application, as long as it matches API level 19, as shown in the right side of Figure 1-2.

Figure 1-2: Standalone mobile application (left) and mobile application with included library (right)

1.4.3 Interaction of Driving Simulators and Android

A typical interaction between the simulators and the mobile devices is shown in Figure 1-3. The modules are connected via TCP-IP sockets due to implementation simplicity. The communication messages are formatted in JSON and therefore the message contents can be easily changed to add different kind of data.

The basic message template contains two compulsory fields, which are *latitude* and *longitude*. Other optional fields are the current *speed*, the GPS *accuracy*, the message *timestamp* or even the *speed limit* from the current location. A specific instantiation of this interaction is discussed in the next section.

Figure 1-3: Typical interaction between IC-DEEP simulator and an ADAS

The coupling of SUMO microscopic simulator with the driving simulators, namely with IC-Deep, uses the same methodology as implemented and described elsewhere [17]. However, this raises some issues regarding the communication channel, as the SUMO TraCI protocol uses sockets and currently does not support more than one active socket. This is obviously a bottleneck when controlling multiple driving agents and a possible SUMO extension to support parallelism in terms of communication is in study.

1.5 Preliminary Verification

The preliminary verification to assess the proof of concept and also the efficiency of the developed architecture focused on the modules in the dotted area of Figure 1-1, the remainder of the system will be developed later on, as mentioned in the next chapter. We have divided the verification into two independent tests. Both of the tests were performed in the same geographical location, which was Porto's downtown, on *Avenida dos Aliados*, as seen in Figure 1-4.

Figure 1-4: Generated 3D Scene ortographic view

In the first experiment we test the simulator accuracy to represent real-world scenarios using the GeoStream framework. The other test aims to emulate the GPS signal on the mobile device.

1.5.4 Simulator Accuracy

To test the simulator accuracy we have collected multiple GPS trace logs while driving a real car in the selected geographical location. We have then overlaid a visual representation of the obtained traces on the simulator and on Google Earth both, the results can be seen in Figure 1-5. The results show that the generated 3D scene is highly representative of the real world location. In one of the trace logs we have noticed an error and highlighted it in Figure 1-5, this error happens due to the data being collected as raw, untreated GPS, where the *road matching* algorithm [18] has not been applied. This is also an interesting result, as the error can be seen in both the simulator and Google Earth alike.

Figure 1-5: GPS traces on the simulator (left) and Google Earth (right)

Apart from testing the fidelity of the simulation with GPS trace logs, it is also noticeable that the ortographic view of the generated 3D scene very much resembles the satellite image of the same location, as it can be seen in Figure 1-6.

Figure 1-6: Satellite image of Av. dos Aliados

1.5.5 Mobile Device ADAS

To test the communication and emulation in the mobile device the setup consisted of a basic usage scenario, using a simple *ADAS* that shows the user his current and average speed, the total kilometers traveled, and, most importantly, warns him when he exceeds the speed limit of the current location as shown in Figure 1-7.

The interaction between the simulator and the mobile application followed that of Figure 1-3. To run the simulation the mobile application must be started and the device's IP address, which is shown in the application initial screen, must be entered in the simulator configuration screen. After this the simulation can start and the simulator internally updates the geographical coordinates as the driver traverses the network. These coordinates are passed on to the mobile device as described above, every second and via a JSON formatted message over a TCP-IP socket.

Figure 1-7: Developed ADAS

In this particular simulation the information sent to the mobile device consists of the current GPS coordinates and the speed limit of the current location. The heading of the vehicle is calculated internally by the mobile application using a simple algorithm that computes the bearing with the last two known locations and thus, even though this can be done easily, there is no need to pass on an orientation variable from the simulator.

The main goal of this experimentation was to understand whether or not the mobile device simulated GPS position and calculated speed matched those of the simulator. We have used the driving simulator and Google Maps application to compare the marked position while driving. To compare the driving speed we have used the developed ADAS.

Even though the results from the simulator and the mobile device were not recorded, any inaccuracies were not noticed when testing. The only possible minor differences would be due to the fact that the Google Location API on the Android device automatically adjusts the current position to the nearest road, which is, as mentioned above, a technique called *road matching*.

1.6 Conclusion

In this paper we presented a multi-faceted MAS-based driving simulator methodology. The presented framework can be used to simulate and test multiple aspects in human factors in ITS, generally. Among others we identify some that we consider more expressive of the system's spread, such as supporting a Serious Game [19] to test driving behaviours and

ergonomics, simulating driver's idiosyncrasies effects on the ATS with peer-designed agents, and also prototyping and validating Advanced Driver Assistance Systems.

The preliminary verification has illustrated the system efficiency and usability, as well as its ability to accurately represent real-world scenarios without the need of extensive 3D modeling or expensive hardware setups. This ability allows researchers to conduct studies regarding singularities of the different geographical locations.

As a great advantage over other systems we point out the fact that our system is always up to date in terms of real-world mapping, and also that there is no need to waste any time creating a scene when the sole purpose is to test an ADAS or do any other kind of simulation.

In addition to implementing the remaining components of the proposed methodology, there is an ambitious workload of further developments. We would like to point out some that we consider priority and more challenging. We believe it would be interesting to support batch simulations, in order to collect significant data and extract more elaborate conclusions. There are also improvements specific to driving simulators that we envisage, such as more detailed scenarios and improved physics.

It would also be interesting to develop cache servers that could store the responses from external services, and thus improve loading times. Another interesting enhancement would be to allow multiple agents to connect to multiple ADAS, simulating distributed ADAS applications while extending SUMO capabilities. There are also refinements to be done in the GeoStream framework, specially regarding road generation and also importing models and textures for different buildings.

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